

CFD Analysis of Heat Conduction Model for TRISO Nuclear Fuel

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ABSTRACT

High temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) and Heat pipe-cooled reactors (HPRs) are being actively developed as a next generation power source. Numerous designs of HTGRs and HPRs are adopting TRISO nuclear fuel to ensure a reactor safety and efficiency. In this study, a detailed 3-dimensional (3D) heat conduction analysis of nuclear fuel containing TRISO particles is performed using the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code, STAR-CCM+. By applying internal heat generation conditions within the fuel, the thermal conductivity (k_{eff}) of the fuel is derived. A representative 3D model is constructed, explicitly modeling 221 randomly distributed TRISO particles in a layer within the graphite matrix. A constant heat source of 20 MW/m³ is applied within the TRISO particles, simulating fission heat. A constant temperature of 1,100 K was assumed for the outer surface of the fuel slug, while symmetric boundary conditions are applied to the top and bottom surfaces to represent a longer fuel rod. The analysis revealed that the effective thermal conductivity derived from the detailed CFD is 14.963 W/m·K. When this value was compared with conventional thermal conductivity models (Series, Parallel, and Maxwell), it showed a large difference value with the Series model and significant differences with the Parallel and Maxwell models as well. This suggests that existing simplified correlations have limitations in accurately predicting the complex heat conduction characteristics of TRISO fuel and may contain substantial errors. Therefore, for precise thermal performance evaluations of HTGRs and HPRs, new effective thermal conductivity correlations that reflects the unique properties of the fuel need to be developed.

Keywords: High temperature gas-cooled reactor, Heat pipe-cooled reactor, Tri-structural Isotropic (TRISO) fuel, Conduction Heat Transfer, Computational Fluid Dynamics

1. INTRODUCTION

High temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) have been developed for several centuries and they are expected to be deployed in several years for multiple purposes of supplying electricity and also high temperature heat sources. In addition, heat pipe-cooled reactors (HPRs) for space exploration, remote regions, and polar applications are also actively developed all over the world. As an innovative micro reactor, the HPR holds the potential to open new markets and be applied in various fields. This reactor is small and transportable, making it useful as a power source for remote areas or military bases that are difficult to connect to existing power grids. It also has the advantage of stable operation in extreme environments such as polar regions and space. The heat pipe reactor allows for modular construction, where most components are manufactured in a factory and assembled on-site, which can be advantageous for shortening construction periods, reducing costs, and ensuring the safety of on-site workers.

In many designs of HTGRs and HPRs, a fuel form consisting of TRISO particles within a graphite matrix is adopted. This type of fuel is evaluated as being advantageous for securing the Defense-in-Depth of the HGTRs and HPRs, which has a simple structure. Accurately evaluating the heat transfer

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performance from the nuclear fuel to the heat pipe is one of the most critical parts of ensuring the reactor's safety, efficiency, and reliability.

2. TRISO Fuel Heat Conductivity

A core of HPRs generally has an arrangement where nuclear fuel and heat pipes are inserted into a structural body. In this configuration, if the heat transfer between nuclear fuel and heat pipes is unstable, localized overheating can be encountered, it may change the physical properties and cause the crack, thus threatening the structural integrity of the reactor. Therefore, through an accurate heat transfer modeling, it is necessary to predict the temperature distribution of each component modeling and evaluate the materials' durability against thermal stress to design it so that structural defects do not occur during its operational lifetime. Furthermore, evaluation of accurate heat transfer model and analysis of temperature distribution are important for assessing the reactivity feedback corresponding to temperature changes.

2.1 TRISO Heat Conduction Model

Recently the Westinghouse developed eVinci™ HPR, which adopts TRISO (TRi-structural ISOtropic) fuel [1]. TRISO particles, with a diameter of less than 1 mm, surround the nuclear fuel with multiple layers of coating and function as a small-size containment vessel to confine the radioactive materials themselves. Nuclear fuel kernel, located in center of TRISO, normally is composition of UO₂ (Uranium Dioxide) or UC (Uranium Carbide), is a region where thermal power is generated through the nuclear fission. And the fuel kernel is protected by multiple layers: a porous carbon layer, an inner pyrolytic carbon layer, a silicon carbide layer, and an outer pyrolytic carbon layer.

The methodology for evaluating the effect the effective thermal conductivity of fuel assemblies numerous TRISO coated particles is based on the heat transfer theory of composite materials. Since the TRISO fuel assembly is a composite of TRISO particles and a matrix (usually graphite), the overall thermal conductivity of the assembly depends on the thermal conductivities and volume fractions of the individual components. The most common methods proposed for evaluating the effective thermal conductivity of a TRISO fuel assembly include the Series model, Parallel model, and Maxwell model [2].

The Series model assumes that heat flow serially through the two materials. It provides the minimum value of effective thermal conductivity, and it also can be predicted less value than actual value. This model calculates the thermal conductivity using the following equation (1).

$$\frac{1}{k_{eff}} = \frac{f_p}{k_p} + \frac{1-f_p}{k_m} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, k_p is the heat conductivity if TRISO particles, k_m is the heat conductivity of matrix, and f_p is a volume fraction of TRISO particles.

The Parallel model is established under the assumption that heat flows in parallel through the two materials. It provides the maximum value of effective thermal conductivity value, and also can be overestimation of the actual value. This model calculates the thermal conductivity using the following equation (2).

$$k_{eff} = f_p k_p + (1 - f_p)k_m \quad (2)$$

The Maxwell models was established assuming spherical particles are dispersed in a continuous matrix. Considering the TRISO particles are spherical, this model can be seen as more applicable to the actual phenomenon.

$$k_{eff} = \frac{k_m\{2k_m + k_p - 2f_p(k_m - k_p)\}}{\{2k_m + k_p + f_p(k_m - k_p)\}} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Computational Analysis Model.

Recently, computational analysis methods such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) have been widely used to accurately model the complex structure of TRISO fuel assemblies. In these methods, the geometric structures of the TRISO particles and the matrix are implemented in a 3D model.

The TRISO particles are randomly replaced like actual distribution. For material properties input, it is necessary to secure the thermal conductivity depended on temperature and other thermophysical properties of each component (fuel kernel, buffer, PyC, SiC, matrix). Also, the heat source generated in the fuel kernel must be defined and applied to the model. Finally, the effective thermal conductivity of entire assembly can be inversely evaluated using the calculated temperature distribution and total heat flux. Such computational analysis can precisely consider not only the thermal conductivity of each component but also interface contact resistance, the effect of pores, and even radiation heat transfer between particles, making it considered the most reliable evaluation method.

3. Evaluation of TRISO Fuel Matrix by STAR-CCM+ Code

The heat transfer rate is calculated by using STAR-CCM+ [3] in condition that fission heat is generated by nuclear fission from the fuel of an HPR. The validity of the model was evaluated through detailed thermal analysis by comparing the results with the temperature distribution from existing thermal conduction model.

3.1 Nuclear Fuel Thermal Analysis Model

In a typical HPR, nuclear fuels are loaded along a rod form within an assembly block, and TRISO particles are distributed within these pellets. Figure 1 shows the configurations where TRISO particles are dispersed within the fuel matrix.

Figure 1. TRISO fuel configuration [4].

To evaluate heat transfer analysis from the nuclear fuel of an HPR containing TRISO fuel particles using the STAR-CCM+ code, a part of the nuclear fuel was configured as shown in Figure 2. This model assumes 20 MW/m^3 of heat generated from the TRISO particles and uses the thermal conductivity of the TRISO particles and the graphite matrix as input. This Figure 2 also depicts the mesh structure for the TRISO particles and the graphite matrix.

Simcenter STAR-CCM+

Figure 2. Modeling of Part of Fuel Rod including TRISO

In the CFD evaluation of the effective thermal conductivity of TRISO fuel compacts, the volume fraction of the TRISO particles and the graphite matrix is the dominant factor [5]. Thus, as shown in Figure 2, to perform a more accurate temperature distribution within the TRISO particle matrix using STAR-CCM+, the distribution of TRISO particles within the fuel matrix was simplified. The spacing between TRISO particles in the fuel matrix was set to 0.1 mm in both radial and axial directions. For the analysis of a portion of fuel rod, the gap at the top and bottom of the TRISO fuel particles was 0.05 mm to maintain the same gap size between TRISO fuel particles in other fuel assemblies. Symmetric boundary conditions were applied to the top and bottom surfaces to simulate a sufficiently long fuel rod. The side boundary was assumed to be maintained at a constant temperature of 1100 K, and continuous heat generation from the nuclear fission was assumed within the TRISO particles. A constant heat source of 20 MW/m³ is applied within the TRISO particles, simulating fission heat. The TRISO fuel matrix has a diameter of 17 mm and a height of 1.9 mm. And TRISO particles with a diameter of 0.85 mm are regularly distributed. This analyzed section of TRISO fuel matrix consists of a total of 442 TRISO particles, arranged in two layers of 221 particles each.

3.2 Evaluation of Sensitivity of TRISO Fuel Matrix Analysis Mesh

When performing temperature analysis within the TRISO fuel matrix, the analysis accuracy can be influenced by the number of analysis cells. Accordingly, a sensitivity analysis was conducted for three cases, as shown in Table I. In table II, it shows the results of maximum temperature in TRISO fuel matrix about the sensitivity evaluation. As shown in Table II, there is no large difference between the Minimum mesh number analysis (230,228 meshes, CASE 1) and the Maximum mesh number analysis (2,572,478 meshes, CASE 2) in sensitivity evaluation. There are visualizations of result of mesh sensitivity evaluation of TRISO fuel matrix

Table I. The number of mesh in TRISO fuel matrix

	CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3
Number of Cell	240,428	2,366,850	2,572,478

Table II. Maximum Temperature of TRISO fuel matrix according to number of mesh.

	CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3
Maximum Temperature (K)	1,106.55	1,107.84	1,107.84

Figure 3. Temperature distribution of TRISO fuel matrix according to number of meshes.

3.3 TRISO Fuel Thermal Analysis by STAR-CCM+

In this study, using the temperature distribution obtained from the STAR-CCM+ analysis, the effective thermal conductivity coefficient within the fuel matrix was calculated and compared against the previously described conventional thermal conductivity correlations. The evaluation of conventional correlations was performed through a STAR-CCM+ calculation on the same fuel model as in Fig. 2. However, in this calculation, meshes for the TRISO particles were not generated; instead, they were modeled by substituting them with a material of equivalent thermal conductivity.

The analysis results showed that there was a significant difference between the detailed CFD model and the series model among the conventional correlations. Conversely, the parallel model and the Maxwell model were calculated to have a relatively small difference from the detailed CFD model. These results confirm that conventional correlations can include significant errors when calculating the thermal conductivity of fuel containing TRISO particles.

Therefore, for a more accurate evaluation of the heat transfer performance of TRISO fuel, it is deemed necessary to secure data on the effective thermal conductivity coefficient that matches the fuel characteristics and to propose new correlations based on this data.

Table III. Comparison of Effective Heat transfer coefficient heat transfer coefficient for heat transfer models

Heat Transfer Model	k_{eff} (W/m·K)	Max. Temp. (K)
Series Model	8.168	1,114.35
Parallel Model	11.454	1,110.24
Maxwell Model	10.777	1,110.88
Detailed CFD	14.963	1,107.84

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a detailed analysis of the thermal conductivity model, which is essential for calculating the heat transfer rate from the fuel to the structure in a heat pipe reactor, was performed using CFD techniques. Through this, the validity of conventionally used thermal conductivity models was confirmed, and this research has established a technical foundation for developing a more accurate thermal conductivity model. In the future, it is expected that the thermal conductivity models of various heat pipe reactors, which will be developed by adopting diverse fuel forms, can be evaluated using the model presented in this study. The effect of random particle distribution and the multi-layered structure of TRISO particles will be investigated to overcome the limitations of the regular lattice model. This will allow for a more accurate assessment of the effective thermal conductivity within a realistic TRISO fuel compact.

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